

An Investigation on External-Internal Drift in Faithfulness Evaluation in Hyperbolic Prototype-based Classifiers

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Abstract

The paper aims to study faithfulness evaluation in hyperbolic prototype-based vision models through the interaction between external perturbation on pixels, and internal perturbation that is geometrically consistent. Although insertion/ deletion based tests are widely used to assess the hypothesis whether salient pixels are substantially capable of affecting model output, they do not by themselves provide evidence whether the induced latent evolution is semantically consistent with the internal geometry of the model. The research addresses the limitation by introducing a two-way framework that compares the external perturbation trajectories with internal tangent-space and geodesic trajectories under a common semantic reference and a common intrinsic progression scale. With this method, a drift measure is introduced, which quantifies the difference between externally effective relevance and internally valid semantic change. Empirically we observed that pixel-based perturbations do not alter genuine faithfulness signal, but the signal is only partially consistent with the semantic structure of the model’s internal structure. The observed discordance can be explained by the perturbation-side effects and the hyperbolic operating regime, especially near the boundary, where geometrical amplification increases the path-dependent variation. We therefore, argue that instead of solely depending on traditional perturbation-based metrics of faithfulness, drift can be considered as a complement how external relevance can align or fail to align, and thus providing a deeper insight into the relationship between external relevance and internal semantic consistency.

Keywords: Hyperbolic learning, prototype-based classification, faithfulness evaluation, explainable AI, computer vision

1 Introduction

Saliency maps at pixel level are a common form of providing post-hoc explanations of deep vision models not only because they represent a similar visual format but also because they allow automatic assessment of the model by perturbation-based faithfulness tests like insertion and deletion [1][2][3]. In real-world processes, saliency is also used to diagnose the failure modes, to determine whether predictions relied on plausible evidence, and to facilitate accountability in cases where predictive accuracy is no longer considered a sufficient concern of reliable behavior [4][5][6][7][8]. Faithfulness analysis is based on the idea that an explanation can be viewed as an intervention statement: given a set of input coordinates, the critical ones should be determined; the controlling adjustments of the input coordinates must result in changes in the model response in a predictable direction. By this principle the perturbation curves and protocols of retraining are motivated, as well as formal criteria like infidelity and sensitivity, wherein the explanations are in regard to how the model responds to perturbations[1][2][9][10]. However, the notion of consistent direction is dependent on how perturbations are parametrized, the selection of baselines and the fact that perturbed inputs are described as belonging to

a distribution where the encoder of a model acts in a predictable way[3][11][12][13].

Hyperbolic representation learning brings in another problem of ambiguity. Hyperbolic representations are used to encode hierarchical structure in the form of a compact code[14][15], and modern hyperbolic neural networks use exponential maps, Möbius operations, and Riemannian optimization in end-to-end models[16][17][18], and vision-oriented architectures [19][20][21]. In this type of model, pixel perturbations are operative in Euclidean input space, and the semantics of the head are operational in hyperbolic representation space. The question of whether a pixel saliency ranking passes insertion/deletion tests is not the point, though, but whether the dynamics of the representation caused by pixel interventions are geometrical in the semantic space of the model. The presented methodology formalizes a pair-wise faithfulness analysis that compares external (perturbations in pixel space) and internal (perturbations that are geometry consistent) perturbations using a common semantic measure pointing towards a combination of the two approaches to demonstrate how each of the two approaches differentiates or becomes useful to the other.

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2 Related Literature

Saliency algorithms produce the probability distributions of input coordinates to explain the conditional dependency between a model output and its input representation[4]. Initial research used gradients of a class score of pixel intensities, and the results were saliency maps including those generated by the Deep Inside Convolutional Networks. Later developments in feature visualisation and deconvolutional analysis led to a more general saliency paradigm that can be used throughout the computer-vision fields[1].

Intermediate activations provide spatial explanations that are of Class Activation Mapping (CAM) -like families, which are strong at the cost of ultra-spatial granularity. The CAM framework proposed the global average pooling and class localised weights over localised discriminative regions; Grad-Cam added weights based on the gradients of feature map. Grad-CAM+ also optimizes this weighting by considering a large number of instances, whereas Score-CAM does not use explicit gradient dependence by instead using forward-pass scoring of activation maps. Ablation-CAM is a gradient-free localisation method based on ablation analysis that uses relevance based on ablation analysis without gradient data[6][22][23][24][25].

Noise -average techniques, such as *SmoothGrad*, improve the visual quality of gradient-based sensitivity maps by averaging them across a large number of noise-corrupted copies of the input[26].

The axiomatic and decomposition-based attribution schemes find relevance based on the baseline inputs or using distribution of relevance by pixel. Formalisation of axioms, the propagation of activation discrepancies with respect to reference points is a part of Sensitivity and Implementation Invariance, and pixel-wise relevance decomposition algorithms such as Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP), which can be applied to individual model classes[27][28][29][30].

Faithfulness testing attempts to fix the inconsistency of plausible heatmaps with faithful representations of the decision logic of a model. Insertion/deletion curves, such as RISE, DAUC/IAUC and the Pointing Game, offer a ranking measure, which traces the change in target production of the sequential feature insertion/deletion. Additional methods of testing a perturbation-based explanation are: Region Perturbation, AOPC/ MoRF/ LeRF, and Sanity Checks of Saliency Metrics. ROAR assesses the approximate feature importance through the process of excising and retraining; the evaluation is connected to learnability after excision. Infidelity and sensitivity provide formal computation of linking explanation vectors to output perturbations, which sheds light on dependence on perturbation distributions. Removal-based unification Removal-based unification such as Explaining by Removing, proves that a large variety of methods of explanation can be presented as approximations of feature removal[1][2][3].

Two strands of critique characterise a defensible methodology. In the first place, explanations have been proved insanity checking: randomisation tests indicate

that some saliency methods are insensitive to model parameters or data noise; input invariance tests indicate that such methods are insensitive to transformations that fix prediction errors to first order; fragility experiments indicate that explanations can be arbitrarily manipulated, leaving prediction errors unchanged to first order; and manipulation experiments indicate that explanations can be arbitrarily manipulated, causing prediction errors to change only to first order. This can be supported by literature on Sanity Checks of Saliency Maps, Revisiting Sanity Checks and Sanity Checks of Saliency Metrics[31].

Second, it is confounded during evaluation ROAD shows that perturbation-based evaluation is sensitive to mask-shape leakage, and suggests more consistent evaluation procedures; the DAUC/IAUC criticism says that area-under-curve measures of insertion/deletion are primarily dependent on ranking, rather than magnitude, and can be biased by out-of-distribution perturbations, thus invalidating the interpretation of metrics. These issues are expressed in ROAD, the DAUC/IAUC criticism as well as the Sanity Checks of Saliency Metrics. The Quantus framework arranges the assessment process by providing a set of full-scale metrics and promoting the controlled experimental design[3][7][13].

To learn hierarchical structures, hyperbolic representation learning has been added to modern machine-learning architectures, with Poincare embeddings being an example that is optimised using alternative formulations like the Lorentz model to optimise the learning process and scale[14]. Hyperbolic neural networks make use of Möbius operations and hyperbolic logistic -regression-type heads, trained with Riemannian optimisation methods, such as Riemannian stochastic gradient descent and adaptive optimisers[18]. The current range of hyperbolic vision research is hyperbolic image embeddings, hyperbolic vision transformers, hyperbolic image-text representations (MERU), and fully hyperbolic convolutional archetypes, including resnet-inspired ones[21].

The application of geodesics, exponential maps, arc-length parameterisations and length minimising properties herein is a canonical construction of Riemannian geometry[32]. Manifold optimization provides algorithmic abstractions and notation standards, which are consistent with the empirical learning of hyperbolic networks[33].

3 Geometry-Aware Saliency and Measurement Goals Of The Faithfulness Evaluation

To an academic point of view, saliency maps are best seen as small-scale models of local dependence, and not direct causal explanations[34][35][36]. Gradient -based maps measure the sensitivity on the micro -level; CAM -style maps measure the spatial significance of the intermediate activations; and baseline -integrated and decomposition -based measures evaluate the contribution relative to a selected baseline [4][6][8][22]. Therefore,

the concept of fidelity must be interpreted as something complex and not a universal quality [9].

In practice, to evaluate a ranking of salient features, insertion/deletion tests are commonly used to define whether a given perturbation operator is consistent with a result of a predefined ranking [1]. The model is disturbed by a progressively disturbed input, and the measure is taken of the rate of change of a specified intended response. This method generates insights so long as the perturbation sequence is under a regime that maintains the predictability in the behaviour of the encoder[11][12]. It is however misleading when perturbations cause the data to leave the initial training distribution or unintended cues are introduced by the geometry of the masks that are used[3][2][13].

The hyperbolic model presents an explicit semantic coordinate system: prototype distance heads compute logits as distances in the representation space[15][16]. In turn, distance to the predicted-class prototype is simply a natural head-aligned measure of faithfulness analysis, and a principled yardstick on how faithfully the predictions of a model are based on the underlying semantic geometry[?].

3.1 Model Architecture and Hyperbolic Notations

Let the input image be $x \in [0, 1]^{C \times H \times W}$, and let the network decompose into a parameterized encoder θ_E where $h(x) = \phi(x) \in R^m$ is the body of the encoder E and a hyperbolic head and where $v(x)$ is the projection:

$$h(x) = \phi_{\theta_E}(x) \in R^m$$

$$v(x) = \pi_{\theta_E}(h(x)) = W_{\theta_E}h(x) + b_{\theta_E} \in R^d$$

The hyperbolic model constrains the Euclidean latent magnitude by introducing an explicit constraint map ψ :

$$\bar{v}(x) = \psi(v(x)) \in R^d$$

The hyperbolic head maps $\bar{v}(x)$ into the Poincare ball of curvature $-c$ ($c > 0$)

$$z(x) = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_c^c(\bar{v}(x))) \in D_c^d$$

where $D_c^d = \{z \in R^d : c\|z\|^2 < 1\}$ is the Poincare ball with curvature $-c$ ($c > 0$) [14]. A standard closed form for the exponential map at the origin in the Poincare ball is[16],

$$\exp_c^c(v) = \tanh(\sqrt{c}\|v\|) \frac{v}{\sqrt{c}\|v\|}$$

(with the convention $\exp_c^c(0) = 0$). To guarantee $z(x)$ stays strictly inside D_c^d in finite precision, a common radial projection is

$$\text{Proj}_c(z) = z \cdot \min\left(1, \frac{1-\varepsilon}{\sqrt{c}\|z\|}\right),$$

with $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ and $\text{Proj}_c(0) = 0$.

Prototypes are parameters θ_P defining points $p_k(\theta_P) \in D_c^d$, $k = 1, \dots, K$. Class logits are defined by a distance-based rule with temperature $\tau > 0$:

$$\ell_k(z) = -\tau \cdot d_c(z, p_k)^2$$

and the predicted class is $\hat{y}(x) = \text{argmax}_k \ell_k(z(x))$. We apply the closed form of the Poincare distance

$$d_c(u, v) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{c}}\right) \cdot \text{arcosh}\left(1 + \frac{2c\|u-v\|^2}{(1-c\|u\|^2)(1-c\|v\|^2)}\right)$$

with $\text{arcosh}(\cdot)$ the inverse hyperbolic cosine. In the Poincare ball, the metric tensor is conformal to Euclidean coordinates:

$$g_c(z) = \lambda_c(z)^2 I$$

$$\lambda_c(z) = \frac{2}{1-c\|z\|^2}$$

which grows without bound as $\|z\|$ approaches $\frac{1}{\sqrt{c}}$ (the boundary)[14][37].

3.2 Geometry-Aware Saliency for Metric Correction

Assuming that the target score is the logit of the predicted class. By specifying the predicted-class prototype to be $\hat{p} = p_{\hat{y}(x)}$ and state the score to be [14][16],

$$S(x) = \ell_{(\hat{y}(x))}(z(x)) = -\tau \cdot d_c(z(x), \hat{p})^2$$

A geometry-sensitive saliency approach assigns significance in a geometry intensive isotope of the z -space. The Riemannian gradient provides the mathematically intrinsic steepest-ascent direction of a scalar field on a Riemannian manifold, which is given by [17][37],

$$\left\langle \text{grad}_R \tilde{S}(z), w \right\rangle_{g_c(z)} = d\tilde{S}(z)[w] \text{ for all } w \in T_z D_c^d$$

In which, $\tilde{S}(z) = \ell_{(\hat{y}(x))}(z)$ denotes the same score considered as a function of z and $\langle a, b \rangle_{g_c(z)} = a^T g_c(z) b$ is the metric induced inner product[37]. Since the Poincare metric is conformal, the Riemannian and Euclidean gradients are associated by the usual coordinate identity[16].

$$\text{grad}_R \tilde{S}(z) = g_c(z)^{-1} \cdot \text{grad}_E \tilde{S}(z)$$

With the notation, whereby $g_c(z) = \lambda_c(z)^2 I$, we find and derive $g_c^{-1}(z) = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_c(z)^2}\right)I$, hence[16],

$$\text{grad}_R \tilde{S}(z) = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_c(z)^2}\right) \cdot \text{grad}_E \tilde{S}(z)$$

Replacing or substituting the expression of the conformal factor $\lambda_c(z) = \frac{2}{1-c\|z\|^2}$, and we yield,

$$\text{grad}_R \tilde{S}(z) = \left(\frac{(1-c\|z\|^2)^2}{4}\right) \cdot \text{grad}_E \tilde{S}(z)$$

In order to achieve pixel level saliency, reverse the Riemannian gradient of the embedding map, $z(x)$ ¹. Flatten the input x to become $\tilde{x} \in R^n$ with $n = C \cdot H \cdot W$ and express the Jacobian of z with respect to x as [4],

$$J_x = \frac{\partial z(\tilde{x})}{\partial \tilde{x}} \in R^{d \times n}$$

Now we determine the geometry-sensitive saliency vector [4][16].

$$s(x) = J_x^T \cdot \text{grad}_R \tilde{S}(z(x)) \in R^n$$

An assignment of ranks to pixels ρ is induced by ranking the coordinates of $|s(x)|$ (or first aggregating $|s(x)|$ among colour channels and then ranking the resulting spatial coordinates). This process is a metric-correct steepest-ascent direction in hyperbolic space dragged back to the input by the differential of the model and thus is the canonical way of describing sensitivity on composed maps[4][27].

3.3 Known limitations of Saliency Maps and Relation to Hyperbolic Measurements

There are two strands of critique which are of specific importance. To begin with, explanations may not pass simple tests of sanity: attributions may fail invariance, may fail to change with hyperparameters of a model, or may be perturbed to modify model predictive behaviour[31][36][38][39][40]. Second, the evaluation process can be affected by distributional and methodological problems: perturbations can result in out-of-distribution inputs and AUC-based metrics can be dominated by ranking artefacts, and information leakage by mask geometries [2][3][13]. Specifically, ROAD points out that occlusion-type assessment can actually reward the mask itself and not the underlying substantive content that has been cleared and thus underlines the need to exercise strong debiasing and sensible selection of the operator [2][3]. All of these criticisms encourage the development of assessment protocols that seek to use more than one insertion/ deletion AUC measure, with multiple baselines, controls and diagnostic checks.

3.3.1 Hyperbolic Representations

Specialized spaces Hyperbolic spaces have been built into modern machine-learning systems to support compact modelling of hierarchies[14]. The Lorentz model offers continuous hierarchies and maximization benefits[15]. Hyperbolic neural networks represent neural building blocks in hyperbolic space, and they

¹Although $s(x)$ is indexed by pixel coordinates, it is not the same object as a plain Euclidean pixel-gradient $\nabla_x S(x)$. The metric correction is applied in representation space: $\text{grad}_R \tilde{S}(z) = g_c(z)^{-1} \nabla_z \tilde{S}(z)$. The pullback $J_x^T(\cdot)$ then transports this *hyperbolic* steepest-ascent direction to the input. If we instead used $\nabla_x S(x)$ directly, the steepest-ascent direction would be measured in Euclidean coordinates of z , ignoring the position-dependent scaling induced by g_c . Thus, the result is a pixel-space vector but derived from a geometry-correct direction in z -space.

use distance-based heads[16], which are trained using Riemannian optimisation methods [17][18]. Applications that are vision-based include hyperbolic image embeddings and full end-to-end hyperbolic systems [19][41][42][43][44]. Theoretical diagnostics work on a theory of geodesics, the exponential map, and length minimising properties of base texts in geometry that are to be used in subsequent work.

3.3.1.1 Saliency and Faithfulness in Hyperbolic Representations

The saliency maps can be best described as an overview of local dependence as opposed to a direct causal explanation. Gradient-based maps measure local sensitivity; CAM-style maps measure the spatial usefulness of intermediate activations; baseline-based methods measure contributions to a reference input. Since these modalities are different concepts, the idea of faithfulness cannot be narrowed down to one universal property. Insertion-deletion tests are empirically used to test or gauge the correspondence between a proposed ranking and a specified perturbation operator: inputs to the model are perturbed partially, and the metric captures how the target response varies[1]. These tests are informative on regimes where the perturbation sequence is within a regime where the encoder is predictable; otherwise, they can be misleading either when the perturbations cause the input to lie beyond the training distribution or when mask geometry brings in other cues[13]. A strong approach to this, then, does not see insertion-deletion as a sign of faithfulness but as one possible approach to sensitivity in the presence of a given set of interventions, supplemented with controls and geometry-conscious diagnostics[7][11].

Hyperbolic models add an extra dimension that can be measured: since in a head is being operated in a distance-based space, researchers are able to determine the probability or logit behaviour on the perturbed inputs and how the internal representation changes relative to the prototype using the hyperbolic metric. This feature allows defining in detail what is meant by semantic motion, in a head-aligned coordinate frame and allows exploring how external pixel perturbations together with internal geometry-congruent motions result in a shared explanatory narrative.

4 Problem Statement and Theoretical Diagnostics

Therefore, given a classifier f , with hyperbolic representation space and a prototype-based head, and an input image x , whose predicted-class is denoted by $\hat{y}(x)$, we form the predicted-class prototype, $\hat{p} = p_{\hat{y}(x)}$, and introduce the head aligned semantic ruler [16],

$$\Delta(z) = d_c(z, \hat{p}) \quad (1)$$

A saliency method provides a ranking ρ of pixel locations of a classification $\hat{y}(x)$. Suppose that a scalar, such as α , is in the range $[0,1]$ or $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, then, for all, consider the binary top-mask denoted by the symbol,

which is called, $M_\alpha \in [0, 1]^{H \times W}$, and is used to select the first $\lfloor \alpha HW \rfloor$ pixels according to ρ : The mask is broadcasted across the color channels when using with input x . By fixing a baseline image $b = B(x)$. The external insertion/ deletion family of operators is then [1],

$$x_{ins}(\alpha) = b \odot (1 - M_\alpha) + x \odot M_\alpha \quad (2)$$

$$x_{del}(\alpha) = x \odot (1 - M_\alpha) + b \odot M_\alpha \quad (3)$$

The resulting representation-space trajectories are those which are the composition of the entire embedding map,

$$z(\cdot) = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(\bar{v}(\cdot))) \quad (4)$$

Therefore, by composition of (Eq.4) with (Eq.2) and (Eq.3), we derive

$$z_{ins}^{ext(\alpha)} = z(x_{ins}(\alpha)) \quad (5)$$

$$z_{del}^{ext(\alpha)} = z(x_{del}(\alpha)) \quad (6)$$

After plugging them in $z(\cdot)$, i.e., substituting (Eq. 2) into (Eq. 5) and (Eq. 3) into (Eq. 6) and then expanding $z(\cdot)$ using (Eq. 4), we derive the points in the ball,

$$z_{ins}^{ext(\alpha)} = z(x_{ins}(\alpha)) = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(\bar{v}(x_{ins}(\alpha)))) \quad (7)$$

$$z_{del}^{ext(\alpha)} = z(x_{del}(\alpha)) = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(\bar{v}(x_{del}(\alpha)))) \quad (8)$$

Geometry-consistent internal trajectories are specified between one common endpoint of $z(b) = z_0$ between $z(x) = z_1$. These paths can be realized either by interpolation in v -space using coordinate-masked hyperbolic geodesic $\gamma(t)$ connected between z_0 and z_1 , then exponential \exp_0^c followed by projection Proj_c of coordinate-masked forms, or directly in the z -space (Eq. 7)–(Eq. 8) at $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$. [16][37].

Does the external trajectory, $z^{ext(\cdot)}$ induced by the pixel-space ranking ρ of the operator family (Eq. 2)–(Eq. 3) $x \mapsto x_{ins}(\alpha)$ or $x \mapsto x_{del}(\alpha)$, provides semantic progress toward \hat{p} consistent with the internal trajectory $z^{int(\cdot)}$ of the same endpoints $[z_0, z_1]$ when semantic progress is measured by $\Delta(\cdot)$ (Eq.1) and compared after reparameterization by intrinsic hyperbolic arc-length [37][45]?

This issue breaks down into two issues that are related to each other,

- The external query is whether the ranking ρ is such that the insertion/deletion curves (under (Eq.2)–(Eq.3)) of the ranking will do better than the random ranking of ρ_{rnd} the chosen operator family (b, B, M_α) [1][2][3].
- The geometry-consistency question is whether the semantic trajectory $\Delta(z^{ext(s)})$ using (Eq.1) evaluated along the external trajectory (Eq.7)–(Eq.8) is

consistent with $\Delta(z^{int(s)})$ when they are placed on a common intrinsic coordinate (s) (arc length normalisation) and when trivial endpoint effects are eliminated by endpoint-normalized progress [37].

4.1 Euclidean stability diagnostics

The role of Euclidean diagnostics is used to prove not that monotonicity of insertion/deletion curves of arbitrary deep models, but to demonstrate that, when the smoothness condition is met, the behavior of the response to masking is determined by the magnitude of the perturbation in the Euclidean norm. In addition, Euclidean geometry lacks a location-dependent metric scaling analog of the hyperbolic boundary effect²

4.1.1 Proposition E³1 Lipschitz stability

Lipschitz stability of perturbation responses in the Euclidean models[47][48].

Assume that $F : R^n \rightarrow R$ is L -Lipschitz in the Euclidean norm i.e.

$$|F(a) - F(b)| \leq L \|a - b\|_2 \text{ for all } a, b \in R^n \quad (9)$$

Let $\tilde{x} \in R^n$ represent the flattened image ($n = C \cdot H \cdot W$) and let $\tilde{b} \in R^n$ represent a flattened baseline. By specifying a binary mask, denoted by $m_\alpha \in [0, 1]^n$, (the flattened and channel-broadcast variant of M_α) the family of masks, by denoting as [1]

$$\tilde{x}_\alpha = \tilde{x} + m_\alpha \odot (\tilde{b} - \tilde{x}) \quad (10)$$

Then for any α, β applying the Lipschitz bound (Eq. 9) to the pair $(\tilde{x}_\alpha, \tilde{x}_\beta)$ from (Eq. 10),

$$|F(\tilde{x}_\alpha) - F(\tilde{x}_\beta)| \leq L \|\tilde{x}_\alpha - \tilde{x}_\beta\|_2 \quad (11)$$

Using the identity obtained by subtracting (Eq. 10) at α and β , $\tilde{x}_\alpha - \tilde{x}_\beta = (m_\alpha - m_\beta) \odot (\tilde{b} - \tilde{x})$, we get,

$$|F(\tilde{x}_\alpha) - F(\tilde{x}_\beta)| \leq L \left\| (m_\alpha - m_\beta) \odot (\tilde{b} - \tilde{x}) \right\|_2 \quad (12)$$

As the entries of each of $m_\alpha - m_\beta \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$ and one has $|(m_\alpha - m_\beta)_i| \leq 1$, we have

$$\left\| (m_\alpha - m_\beta) \odot (\tilde{b} - \tilde{x}) \right\|_2 \leq \left\| \tilde{b} - \tilde{x} \right\|_2 \quad (13)$$

and therefore,

$$|F(\tilde{x}_\alpha) - F(\tilde{x}_\beta)| \leq L \left\| \tilde{b} - \tilde{x} \right\|_2 \quad (14)$$

Specifically, bounded variations in the response are caused by incremental variations in the mask (measured

²In Euclidean geometry the metric is constant everywhere[37][46].

$$g(x) = I \Rightarrow \|u\|_{g(x)} = \sqrt{u^T I u} = \|u\|_2$$

³Euclidean

by $\left\| (m_\alpha - m_\beta) \odot (\tilde{b} - \tilde{x}) \right\|_2$ and in turn, so long as the underlying response function is Lipschitz, and the perturbation scale is bounded, the response of $\alpha \mapsto F(\tilde{x}_\alpha)$ is stable.

Why does this matter? In Euclidean contexts, Lipschitz continuity is a canonical stability property: it is a condition that ensures that the score curve of progressively masked inputs cannot vibrate arbitrarily quickly unless the perturbations themselves are large, in Euclidean terms[9][49].

4.1.2 Proposition E2 Geodesic Minimality and Constant Metric Scale

Let $a, b \in R^d$, and by identifying the straight-line curve.

$$\gamma(t) = (1-t)a + tb, \quad t \in [0, 1] \quad (15)$$

By differentiating (Eq.15), we derive $\gamma'(t) = b - a$, hence the speed $\|\gamma'(t)\|_2 = \|b - a\|_2$ of this curve γ (Euclidean) is unchanging, and its Euclidean length is [37].

$$L(\gamma) = \int_0^1 \|\gamma'(t)\|_2 dt = \|b - a\|_2 \quad (16)$$

In addition, the length of any absolutely continuous curve $\eta : [0, 1] \rightarrow R^d$, with $\eta(0) = a$ and $\eta(1) = b$ its length⁴ [37]

$$L(\eta) = \int_0^1 \|\eta'(t)\|_2 dt \geq \|b - a\|_2 \quad (17)$$

In Euclidean latent spaces, the motion between endpoints is unambiguous: geodesics are straight line and the length of geodesic is the distance between the endpoints, and the scale of the metric is everywhere equal. As a result, there are no timing distortions due to curvature as in arc-length parameterization. Out-of-distribution inputs and mask-shape leakage can also confound external perturbation, but no further geometry-dependent magnification mechanism as that of the hyperbolic boundary amplification that is mediated⁵ by $\lambda_c(z)$.

4.2 Hyperbolic Stability Diagnostics

In hyperbolic representation models, e.g. the Poincare ball, perturbations of the Euclidean-scale input may result in embedding curves, which have strong intrinsic hyperbolic properties which are highly localized to their location, within the ball. This is due to the fact that the Poincare metric includes a location-dependent scale factor, the distances and arc-lengths increase when one is approaching the boundary. In turn, an externally induced (pixel-driven) trajectory and an internally geometry-consistent trajectory linking the same endpoints can probably be different in head aligned semantic timing when compared in terms of hyperbolic distance coordinates. The methodology section

⁴That is the ‘‘derived from where’’: (Eq. 16) is derived by differentiating (Eq. 15) and applying the length definition; (Eq. 17) is the standard minimality inequality.

⁵The conformal factor is always constant, ruler does not change

formalizes this mismatch as external-internal disagreement under a shared semantic ruler and an intrinsic arc-length parameterization [13][14].

4.2.1 Hypothesis H1 Boundary Amplification of Intrinsic Length

Let

$$D_c^d = \{ z \in R^d : c\|z\|^2 < 1 \}, \quad \text{with } c > 0 \quad (18)$$

is the Poincare ball model of constant curvature $-c$ [14][16].

The Riemannian metric tensor of D_c^d in Euclidean coordinates is conformal,

$$g_c(z) = \lambda_c(z)^2 I \quad (19)$$

with conformal factor becomes

$$\lambda_c(z) = \frac{2}{1 - c\|z\|^2} \quad (20)$$

The implication of (Eq.20) is that there is an amplification of the characteristic boundary as $\lambda_c(z) \rightarrow \infty$ when $\|z\| \rightarrow 1/\sqrt{c}$ (approaching the boundary of D_c^d), which provides the mathematical explanation why distances, lengths blow up when one approaches the boundary of the Poincare ball. To translate the metric into a length formula, we take any tangent vector $u \in R^d$ at point z . By definition, the norm induced by $g_c(z)$ is [37]

$$\|u\|_{g_c(z)} = \sqrt{u^T g_c(z) u} \quad (21)$$

Following we substitute the conformal form (Eq. 19) into (Eq. 21),

$$\begin{aligned} u^T g_c(z) u &= u^T (\lambda_c(z)^2 I) u \\ &= \lambda_c(z)^2 (u^T u) = \lambda_c(z)^2 \|u\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, proceeding with square root gives,

$$\|u\|_{g_c(z)} = \lambda_c(z) \|u\| \quad (22)$$

Let $z : [0, 1] \rightarrow D_c^d$ be a differentiable curve (in Euclidean coordinates). The Riemannian line element along $z(t)$ is by definition that of the form

$$ds = \|z'(t)\|_{g_c(z(t))} dt \quad (23)$$

Substituting (Eq.22) u in the result above with $z'(t)$ and replacing z with $z(t)$, the following is obtained,

$$\|z'(t)\|_{g_c(z(t))} = \lambda_c(z(t)) \|z'(t)\| \quad (24)$$

Hence the line element becomes⁶ [37],

$$ds = \lambda_c(z(t)) \|z'(t)\| dt \quad (25)$$

The arc-length of the hyperbolic is obtained by integrating (Eq. 25) over $t \in [0, 1]$:

⁶By expanding Eq.24 and substituting Eq.23 with the simplified version of Eq.24

$$L_c(z) = \int_0^1 \lambda_c(z(t)) \|z'(t)\| dt \quad (26)$$

If the curve passes through regions where $\|z(t)\|$ is large, then $\lambda_c(z(t))$ is scaling with it. (by Eq. 20), and the identical Euclidean coordinate-speed $\|z'(t)\|$ accumulates greater intrinsic length.

$$L_c(\gamma) = d_c(z_0, z_1) \quad (27)$$

Moreover, any absolutely continuous curve η connecting the same endpoints satisfies the lower bound

$$L_c(\eta) \geq d_c(z_0, z_1) \quad (28)$$

Here, we take $\eta = z_{ext}$, where z_{ext} is the representation trajectory induced by an external perturbation. By combining (Eq. 28) with the definition of length we achieve the wandering score [37],

$$R_{ext} = \frac{L_c(z_{ext})}{d_c(z_0, z_1)} \geq 1 \quad (29)$$

Connecting and synthesizing this to why the external pixel perturbations can wander off, depending on the satisfaction of $L_c(z_{ext}) \geq d_c(z_0, z_1)$, and the ratio $R_{ext} = \frac{L_c(z_{ext})}{d_c(z_0, z_1)} \geq 1$ (Eq.29) to answer if an external perturbation forces the embedding wander toward higher radius, then λ_c rises (Eq. 20), the path length $L_c(z_{ext})$ inflates (Eq. 26), and the external path can become intrinsically long compared to the geodesic distance between its endpoints (Eq. 29). Here, (Eq. 29) is not yet a drift measure. It is a geometric inefficiency test that demonstrates that the representation path induced externally can already be significantly different to the shortest intrinsic motion between the same endpoints. This is one way in which external perturbation curves may become semantically out of step with internal geometry-consistent curves, prior to agreement being ever recorded in the methodology.

In such a case, an external insertion/deletion curve no longer quantifies the process of evidence removal in isolation; it is in all likelihood combines the processes of evidence removal and geometrical or operator-induced trajectory distortion, an example of confounding exactly the phenomenon that perturbation-evaluation criticisms are intended to point to [2][13].

4.2.2 Hypothesis H2 Radial Distance Inflation

Let $r = \|z\|$ with z in D_c^d and $r < \frac{1}{\sqrt{c}}$. Starting with the closed form of the Poincare distance, as used above[14][16],

$$d_c(u, v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{c}} \operatorname{arcosh} \left(1 + \frac{2c\|u - v\|^2}{(1 - c\|u\|^2)(1 - c\|v\|^2)} \right) \quad (30)$$

By assuming $u = 0$ and $v = z$ we observe that $\|u - v\|^2 = \|z\|^2 = r^2$ and $\|u\|^2 = 0$. Substituting into (Eq.30) gives:

$$d_c(0, z) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{c}} \right) \operatorname{arcosh} \left(1 + \frac{2cr^2}{1 - cr^2} \right) \quad (31)$$

Computing the fraction within the inverse hyperbolic cosine:

$$1 + \frac{2cr^2}{1 - cr^2} = \frac{1 - cr^2 + 2cr^2}{1 - cr^2} = \frac{1 + cr^2}{1 - cr^2}$$

hence,

$$d_c(0, z) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{c}} \right) \operatorname{arcosh} \left(\frac{1 + cr^2}{1 - cr^2} \right) \quad (32)$$

By appealing to the usual identity that holds when $|t| < 1$,

$$\operatorname{arcosh} \left(\frac{1 + t^2}{1 - t^2} \right) = 2 \times \operatorname{artanh}(t) \quad (33)$$

Putting $t = \sqrt{c} \times r$ (permissible because $r < \frac{1}{\sqrt{c}}$ implies $|t| < 1$), (Eq.32) becomes,

$$d_c(0, z) = \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{c}} \right) \times \operatorname{artanh}(\sqrt{c} \times r) \quad (34)$$

Differentiating (Eq.34) with respect to r , and using $\frac{d}{dr} \operatorname{artanh}(\sqrt{c}r) = \frac{\sqrt{c}}{1 - cr^2}$ we obtain[14][37],

$$\frac{d}{dr} d_c(0, z) = \frac{2}{1 - c \times r^2} \quad (35)$$

Consequently,

$$\frac{d}{dr} d_c(0, z) \rightarrow \text{infinity as } r \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{c}} \quad (36)$$

(Eq. 34-36) are specific to distance-to-origin. However, they demonstrate the fundamental effect: radial sensitivity diverges near the boundary. To define the analogous effect for a head-aligned ruler, defining $\hat{p} = p_{y(x)}$ and setting $\Delta(z) = d_c(z, \hat{p})$. By applying the basic Lipschitz property of distance-to-a-fixed-point in any metric space:

$$|d_c(a, p) - d_c(b, p)| \leq d_c(a, b) \quad (37)$$

Using (Eq. 37) with $p = \hat{p}$, $a = z$, and $b = z + \delta z$ gives:

$$|\Delta(z + \delta z) - \Delta(z)| \leq d_c(z, z + \delta z) \quad (38)$$

For sufficiently small δz , the local hyperbolic distance can be approximated using the conformal factor $\lambda_c(z)$,

$$d_c(z, z + \delta z) \approx \lambda_c(z) \|\delta z\| \quad (39)$$

where $\lambda_c(z) = \frac{2}{1 - c\|z\|^2}$

Combining (Eq. 38-39) yields,

$$|\Delta(z + \delta z) - \Delta(z)| \lesssim \lambda_c(z) \times \|\delta z\| \quad (40)$$

(Eq.40) provides evidence that an external pixel perturbation can push the induced embedding z_{ext} into a high-radius region (large $\|z_{ext}\|$), where $\lambda_c(z_{ext})$ becomes large. Then even small representation changes δz

can produce substantial differences in Δ . (Eq. 40) shows how local geometric scaling can magnify a given representation perturbation near high-radius regions. It does not specifically imply that every observed external–internal disagreement is boundary-driven; the actual role of this mechanism must be checked empirically by tracking $\lambda_c(z_{ext})$ alongside the drift statistics. Therefore, the mechanism probably⁷ contributes to the understanding of why externally forced pixel trajectories may exhibit semantic timing that deviates from geometry-consistent internal trajectories between the same endpoints[2][3][13][14][37].

5 Methodology

5.1 External interventions Opposed to Internal Interventions

The most important difference is the scope where the intervention is established.

5.1.1 External intervention (Pixel-Space Operator)

By fixing a baseline image $b = B(x)$ and for that base be a pixel ranking ρ . Given for $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, and we define the top-mask $M_\alpha \in [0, 1]^{H \times W}$ that selects the first $\lfloor \alpha HW \rfloor$ pixel locations according to ρ (broadcast across channels when applied to x),

$$M_\alpha = \text{TopMask}(\rho, \alpha) \quad (41)$$

The insertion and deletion routes are [1]

$$x_{ins}(\alpha) = b \odot (1 - M_\alpha) + x \odot M_\alpha \quad (42)$$

$$x_{del}(\alpha) = x \odot (1 - M_\alpha) + b \odot M_\alpha \quad (43)$$

Let the full embedding map be the composition already defined in (Sec. 4),

$$z(\cdot) = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(\bar{v}(\cdot))) \quad (44)$$

The representation paths obtained corresponding to the propagation of these images using the entire model are⁸,

$$z_{ins}^{ext(\alpha)} = z(x_{ins}(\alpha)) = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(\bar{v}(x_{ins}(\alpha)))) \quad (45)$$

$$z_{del}^{ext(\alpha)} = z(x_{del}(\alpha)) = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(\bar{v}(x_{del}(\alpha)))) \quad (46)$$

These are called external since the intervention acts on x (via $x \mapsto x_{ins}(\alpha)$, $x \mapsto x_{del}(\alpha)$) and only then propagates through the learned embedding map or Encoder E in Eq. (44). This is precisely the regime where out-of-distribution effects and mask-shape leakage can enter and contaminate insertion/deletion interpretations[2][10][11][13].

⁷Consult section

⁸Consult Sec. 4

5.1.2 Internal intervention (Representation-Space Operator)

Internal interventions also bypass pixel space and are specified directly on the variables that the head uses, which eliminates most pixel-distribution shift by construction; they are geometry-consistent controls and are not intended to replace the pixel tests. There are two internal families that are defined by space,

In v -space let E be the encoder

$$v_0 = E(b), \quad v_1 = E(x) \quad (47)$$

Let σ be a ranking of coordinates of v (for example by $\left| \frac{\partial \ell_{\underline{y}}}{\partial v} \right|$ evaluated at v_1). For $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, define the coordinate mask $m_\alpha \in [0, 1]^d$ selecting the first $\lfloor \alpha d \rfloor$ coordinates in σ ,

$$m_\alpha = \text{TopMask}(\sigma, \alpha) \quad (48)$$

By defining the tangent insertion and deletion in v -space:

$$v_{ins}^{\tan(\alpha)} = v_0 + m_\alpha \odot (v_1 - v_0) \quad (49)$$

$$v_{del}^{\tan(\alpha)} = v_1 - m_\alpha \odot (v_1 - v_0) \quad (50)$$

Projecting the above points into our manifold ball gives the corresponding internal representation paths,

$$z_{ins}^{\tan(\alpha)} = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(v_{ins}^{\tan(\alpha)})) \quad (51)$$

$$z_{del}^{\tan(\alpha)} = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(v_{del}^{\tan(\alpha)})) \quad (52)$$

The following construction gives an internal removal/reveal family at the latent-coordinate level which is consistent with the removal-based explanation perspective[10][16].

In z -space let,

$$z_0 = z(b), \quad z_1 = z(x) \quad (53)$$

We define the constant-speed hyperbolic geodesic between z_0 and z_1 using Möbius operations. The standard closed form is,

$$\gamma(t) = z_0 \oplus_c(t \otimes_c((-z_0) \oplus_c z_1)), \quad t \in [0, 1] \quad (54)$$

A typical explicit expression for Möbius addition is[14][16],

$$x \oplus_c y = \frac{(1 + 2c\langle x, y \rangle + c\|y\|^2)x + (1 - c\|x\|^2)y}{1 + 2c\langle x, y \rangle + c^2\|x\|^2\|y\|^2} \quad (55)$$

The common explicit expression for Möbius scalar with $t \otimes_c 0 = 0$ multiplication can be stated as such,

$$t \otimes_c x = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{c}} \right) \tanh(t \cdot \text{artanh}(\sqrt{c}\|x\|)) \frac{x}{\|x\|} \quad (56)$$

We define internal insertion/deletion by endpoint selection,

$$z_{ins}^{geo(t)} = \gamma(t), \quad \text{with } \gamma(0) = z_0 \text{ and } \gamma(1) = z_1 \quad (57)$$

$$z_{del}^{geo(t)} = \gamma(1-t) \quad (58)$$

Endpoint-matched non-geodesic control.

By defining Euclidean linear interpolation in coordinates followed by projection,

$$z_{lin}(t) = \text{Proj}_c((1-t)z_0 + tz_1) \quad (59)$$

It shares endpoints with $\gamma(t)$ but is not generally a geodesic; it is used to isolate endpoint coupling effects versus path-geometry effects. This is the default construction that is used in hyperbolic neural networks to accomplish geodesic interpolation with fixed hyperbolic speed.

We identify a scalar response to monitor. Two possible natural choices in hyperbolic prototype heads are [1][2][3],

$$\pi_{\hat{y}}(x) = \text{softmax}(\ell(z(x)))_{\hat{y}} \quad (60)$$

$$\Delta(z) = d_c(z, p_{\hat{y}}) \quad (61)$$

The distance-to-prototype $\Delta(z)$ is head-aligned because $\ell_k(z) = -\tau \cdot d_c(z, p_k)^2$ is monotone in $d_c(z, p_k)$ [3][16].

We compute insertion/deletion curves under ρ and under a random ranking ρ_{rnd} . Differences in AUC between ρ and ρ_{rnd} provide an above-random signal that partially controls for operator-specific artifacts [1][2][3]. Since the critiques of ROAD and DAUC/IAUC show that evaluation is very sensitive to the perturbation operator and can be confounded by OOD inputs and mask leakage, the protocol takes the choice of baseline, B , a variable of experimental interest instead of a default.

Each protocol is compared using the same head-aligned ruler $\Delta(z)$ in Eq. (61). However, their native step parameters (pixel fraction α , latent fraction α , geodesic time t) are not directly comparable. This fundamental methodological reparameterization of each path is to reparametrize it, by using its intrinsic hyperbolic arc-length and compare semantic progress by using a common intrinsic axis.

Given the samples z_0, z_1, \dots, z_T along any path, we define,

$$\delta_t = d_c(z_{t-1}, z_t) \quad (62)$$

$$\ell_t = \sum_{j=1}^t \delta_j \quad (63)$$

$$s_t = \frac{\ell_t}{\ell_T + \varepsilon} \quad (64)$$

Where $s_t \in [0, 1]$.

We define the semantic progress by normalizing the endpoints along the path using the ruler Δ ,

$$P(s_t) = \frac{\Delta(z_0) - \Delta(z_t)}{\Delta(z_0) - \Delta(z_T) + \varepsilon} \quad (65)$$

The above (Eq. 65) ensures $P(0) = 0$ and $P(1) = 1$ across all protocols and images, therefore, comparisons are made on when and why progress occurs, rather than the magnitude of the raw scores, which are known to cause numerical pathologies when the predetermined probabilities are close to zero in deletion.

5.1.3 Two-Way Agreement and Drift

Assume $P_{ext}(s)$ be the progress curve induced by external pixel perturbations (Eq. 45–46 with Eq. 65) and let $P_{int}(s)$ be the progress curve induced by an internal protocol (Eq. 51–52 or Eq. 57–58 with Eq. 65), both evaluated and plotted on the common intrinsic axis s (conceptually by interpolating onto a common grid).

We define,

$$A(P_{ext}, P_{int}) = 1 - \int_0^1 |P_{ext}(s) - P_{int}(s)| ds \quad (66)$$

5.1.3.1 Drift as Complements of Agreement

By defining pointwise drift:

$$D_{int}(s) = |P_{ext}(s) - P_{int}(s)| \quad (67)$$

Then we determine mean and maximum drift,

$$D_{mean} = \int_0^1 D_{int}(s) ds \quad (68)$$

$$D_{maximum} = \sup_{s \in [0,1]} D_{int}(s) \quad (69)$$

Then from (Eq. 66–69) we imply $A = 1 - D_{mean}$. Our midpoint drift is $D_{int}(\frac{1}{2})$.

5.1.3.2 Noise and Drift Bound Hypothesis

The approach to drift is to make qualitative assertions (e.g. drift is noise) allowable but considers drift as the remaining mismatch of external and internal semantics, once endpoint differences and parameterisation differences are eliminated. A basic metric fact (triangle inequality) gives that for any metric space (M, d) and fixed p ,

$$|d(u, p) - d(v, p)| \leq d(u, v) \quad (70)$$

We apply (Eq. 70) to $\Delta(z) = d_c(z, p_{\hat{y}})$,

$$|\Delta(z_{ext}(s)) - \Delta(z_{int}(s))| \leq d_c(z_{ext}(s), z_{int}(s)) \quad (71)$$

By substituting Eq. (71) into the definition of progress (Eq. 65) yields a pointwise drift bound for our shared endpoints,

$$D_{int}(s) \leq \frac{d_c(z_{ext}(s), z_{int}(s))}{\Delta(z_0) - \Delta(z_T) + \varepsilon} \quad (72)$$

This inequality is the most important mathematical fact that translates semantic drift into a quantifiable geometric discrepancy: the semantic drift is regulated by the discrepancy on representation-spaces multiplied by the range of available semantic values.

5.1.3.3 External Perturbation Noise Model

We write the external operator as the intended masking plus an additive artifact term,

$$x_\alpha = b \odot (1 - M_\alpha) + x \odot M_\alpha + \xi_\alpha \quad (73)$$

Here ξ_α represents perturbation artifacts (not actually removal of features in the intended semantic sense, unnatural local statistics, OOD texture effects). This is exactly the kind of confounding formalized in ROAD-style analyses and AUC critiques[2][3][13].

Let $x_\alpha^* = b \odot (1 - M_\alpha) + x \odot M_\alpha$ denote the ideal masked input ($\xi_\alpha = 0$). A first-order expansion of the embedding map $z(\cdot)$ around x_α^* gives:

$$z(x_\alpha) - z(x_\alpha^*) \approx J_z(x_\alpha^*) \cdot \text{vec}(\xi_\alpha) \quad (74)$$

where J_z is the Jacobian of z with respect to the flattened input above. This makes the mechanism explicit, here the external interventions can inject ξ_α , which perturbs z through the local sensitivity of the embedding.

5.1.3.4 Hyperbolic Amplification of Perturbation Noise

When the external-noise model is combined with the theory that was earlier discussed, thus, we can conclude that the external noise of the model probably be used in order to cause the z_{ext} to push deep into the hyperbolic radius, then the hyperbolic distance between any given point of z and the image becomes more distant, thus the same perturbation of the Euclidean-scale representation would translate to greater hyperbolic distance. Formally, in the Poincaré ball, local hyperbolic displacement scales with the conformal factor $\lambda_c(z)$, therefore, causing amplification near the boundary[16][37].

$$d_c(z, z + \delta z) \approx \lambda_c(z) \cdot \|\delta z\| \quad (75)$$

for small δz .

Combining Eq. (74) and Eq. (75) shows us how ξ_α can be amplified when the external path z_{ext} visits regions with large $\lambda_c(z_{ext})$. This is one of the explicit channels by which external (pixel-driven) paths can diverge in semantic timing from internal geometry-consistent paths, even when the perturbation operator is fixed in addition to artefact-driven deviations captured by ξ_α (Eq. 73–74) even with the same endpoints, the mismatch is not only evidence removal, but also operator-induced noise filtered by the model and amplified by position-dependent geometry[13][14][37].

5.1.3.5 Curvature & Clamp Operating Effects

Because the Poincaré ball has Euclidean radius $\frac{1}{\sqrt{c}}$, changing curvature alters the operating regime of the embedding geometry. In particular, the admissible Euclidean radius shrinks as c increases, while the conformal factor $\lambda_c(z) = \frac{2}{1 - c\|z\|^2}$ becomes more steeply varying near the boundary (Eq. 20).

$$r_{ball} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{c}} \quad (76)$$

The radius of the embedding is, within the head, only dependent on the Euclidean norm of the latent variable, and the method of exponential map accomplishes this objective. From $\exp_0^c(v) = \tanh(\sqrt{c}\|v\|) \cdot \frac{v}{\sqrt{c}\|v\|}$, taking norms gives

$$\|z\| = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{c}}\right) \cdot \tanh(\sqrt{c}\|\bar{v}\|) \quad (77)$$

If the model applies a norm clamp $\|\bar{v}\| \leq v_{maximum}$ before \exp_0^c , then (Eq. 77) defines the bound

$$\|z\| \leq \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{c}}\right) \cdot \tanh(\sqrt{c}v_{maximum}) \quad (78)$$

We define the relative radius $\rho(z) = \sqrt{c}\|z\|$. Then Eq. (78) implies

$$\rho(z) \leq \tanh(\sqrt{c}v_{maximum}) \quad (79)$$

and the conformal factor of the hyperbolic manifold can be written as

$$\lambda_c(z) = \frac{2}{1 - \rho(z)^2} \quad (80)$$

Equations (Eq. 79–80) the main implication, even with an active clamp, as the parameter c increases with a fixed $v_{maximum}$, also increases the attainable $\rho(z)$, subsequently which can increase $\lambda_c(z)$ and therefore increase intrinsic sensitivity to small representation perturbations. This does not state that curvature causes drift, rather curvature can issue drift sensitivity by strengthening the amplification term in (Eq. 75). Specifically, because the drift bound is based on the representation-space discrepancy (Eq. 72), a larger $\lambda_c(z_{ext})$ can enhance the intrinsic discrepancy $d_c(z_{ext}, z_{int})$ caused by the same perturbation channel of the same Euclidean-scale (Eq. 74–75), which in turn relaxes the bound in Eq. (72).

5.1.3.6 Two-Way Assessment Essence

Two-way assessment does not replace a test to an internal test, but rather is a consistency test, something that must be the case, does the external perturbation story map to a model in its internal semantic geometry? The method has a number of advantages mathematically:

- It projects assessment to a head aligned quantity (Eq. 61), which is used directly to compute logits. This removes the confusion as to what is being measured.
- It eliminates the mismatch in parameterisation with arc length s (Eq. 62–64). In this case pixel-fraction steps, latent-fraction steps or geodesic-parameter steps have a common intrinsic axis.
- It isolates non-trivial dissent (drift) even in a coupled endpoint. The progress is endpoint-normalised (Eq. 65), and therefore it is impossible to have artificially inflated agreement due to having all the paths to the common endpoint.

- It is in support of theory-supported diagnostics. Lipschitz bounds (Eq. 70–72) and length minimality properties (Eq. 62–64) serve as sanity checks that dislocation between numerical artefacts and geometry induced drift or perturbation induced drift.

The topic of addressing drift and its meaning is the most important. Drift is not necessarily an indicator of failure. Based on the two-way definition, drift signals will occur when external and internal interventions are temporally different in semantic terms with unit intrinsic distance travelled (Eq. 62–64). This disagreement may be understood in two ways:

- Drift can likely be caused by extraneous confounding factors. Where the large value of ξ_α (OOD artefacts, mask leakage, Eq. 73–74), and $z_{ext}(s)$ (Eq. 44–46) are no longer internally controllable (Eq. 47–59), the prediction of semantic drift bound is larger in presence of $d_c(z_{ext}, z_{int})$ (Eq. 72) is large. It means that perturbation operator must be corrected, which does not imply that the model is unfaithful in nature. More realistic perturbations, like learned or inpainting-based replacements, and ROAD-style debiasing are principled solutions.
- Drift may be dominated by geometry amplification. Even simple coordinate transformations may distort fundamental lengths and semantic time. This happens when embeddings go through high-radius space, where trajectories undergo substantial lateral displacement near the boundary. The term drift here refers to the fact that perturbations in pixel space have a strong dependence on the hyperbolic metric, and the analysis in two directions is specifically intended to identify this geometrical origin of error.

Practically, the methodology regards drift as a diagnostic which should be interpreted as a whole part of controls. Agreement should to be reported as both an average and variability measure throughout the samples, not one value, since saliency assessment is data- and operator-sensitive (Eq. 66–69). Drift is to be mentioned together with auxiliary tracked quantities, e.g. radius, and path-length ratios to end point distance (Eq. 62–64, Eq. 75), baselines (e.g., random ranking) or internal controls (e.g., non-geodesic endpoint-matched interpolation).

6 Experiment and Results

Experimental setup. The experiments are conducted on a synthetic dataset because the aim of this study is not to establish a new state-of-the-art classifier, but to analyze the internal and external perturbation mechanisms of a hyperbolic prototype-based model under controlled conditions. Using synthetic data allows the semantic structure, prototype relations, and perturbation effects to be studied in a more interpretable setting, with reduced confounding from uncontrolled

real-world variation. The model used throughout is an RSS-ResNet-based classifier whose Euclidean backbone is coupled to a Poincaré-ball hyperbolic latent space and a distance-based prototype head. Unless otherwise stated, all reported results are obtained with curvature $c = 1.00$. The evaluation is performed on 500 correctly classified test images, and all values in Tables 1–3 and Figures 1–6 are aggregated over this evaluation set. External Pixel, internal Tangent, and internal Geodesic paths are computed for the same images under the same predicted-class target. Curvature-sweep results repeat the same protocol for $c \in \{0.25, 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00\}$.

The analysis of the hyperbolic drift presents the experimental protocol and findings in this section. Our comparisons between external, pixel-level perturbation paths and internal ones include:

- faithfulness to insertion/deletion,
- drift between external and internal progress functions, and
- diagnostic evidence of the operation of an operating regime dominated by its boundaries.

The section provides an empirical comparison of external pixel-space perturbation trajectories and internal geometry- consistent trajectories. The investigation is evaluated in three aspects as outlined above. (Tables 2–3) and (Figures 2–6) all reflect curvature $c = 1.00$ unless indicated otherwise; Table 1 and Figure 1 are summary of the different curvature sweep.

6.1 Evaluation Setup and Path Definitions

Based on the above methodology, we build three perturbation paths of each test image

- An external pixel path (Pixel/external): parameterized by a progressive perturbation of input features.
- An internal tangent-space path (Tangent/internal, v -space): initialized at the starting latent point; and
- An internal geodesic path (Geodesic/internal, z -space): initialized at the same starting latent point.

Hyperbolic distance is computed in the Poincaré ball of curvature c and arc length parameterization is calculated with the hyperbolic metric belonging to the Poincaré ball of curvature c . Standard hyperbolic neural network building blocks are used in internal operations[14][16].

6.2 Faithfulness via Insertion and Deletion

Our metrics of explanation faithfulness are insertion and deletion curves, insertion shows least-to-most informative features by ranking, whereas deletion shows

most-to-least informative features by removing features, and keeping track of the probability of the desired classes, $p(\hat{y} | x)$, after each deletion. The area under the curve (AUC) summarises curves with a greater AUC indicating a more informative reconstruction, and a smaller deletion AUC indicating a faster drop in confidence, signalling more deletion fidelity [1]. Our results are given in two parameterisations (i) the normalised fraction of features, and (ii) the normalised hyperbolic arc length, s .

6.3 Drift metrics between external and internal progress

To compare external and internal perturbations with our model, we define progress functions $prog_{ext}(s)$ and $prog_{int}(s)$ on a common normalized parameter $s \in [0, 1]$, and compute by subtracting them $drift(s) = |prog_{ext}(s) - prog_{int}(s)|$. We summarize drift with:

- drift AUC (mean_s drift) and
- drift max (maximum drift) (max_s drift).

Two-way drift is evaluated for Pixel vs Tangent, Pixel vs Geodesic, and Pixel vs a control path that matches endpoints but removes geometric structure. Drift curves and histograms are shown in Figures (3–4) and summarized numerically in Table 2.

6.4 Operational Regime diagnostics

The main properties of geometric operating regimes are described in terms of the set of quantitative characteristics, namely: (i) external path inefficiency, expressed as $\mathcal{I} = \frac{L_{ext}}{d_c(z_0, z_1)}$, where L_{ext} is the length of the external path and d_c is the hyperbolic distance between the endpoints; (ii) relative radius, $r = \sqrt{c} \|z\|$, such that r measures the boundary proximity of the Poincaré ball boundary; and (iii) amplification of the boundary via the conformal factor $\lambda_c(z)$ increasing sharply as $\|z\|$ approaches near the boundary. To maintain numerical stability, the tangent vectors are norm clamped. We also keep track of clamp saturation fractions — the ratio of iterative steps to clamp. These diagnostics allow to offer a fine-grained model on how to interpret the patterns of observed drift and explain failure modes (see Figures 4–5).

6.5 Curvature sweep

To make sure that no conclusions are dependent on the choice of a particular curvature, we perform the analysis with $c \in \{0.25, 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00\}$. We present mean drift AUC, mean relative radius, clamp saturation, and path inefficiency of every curvature (Table 1; Figure 1).

6.6 Results

6.6.1 Curvature Sweep Results

Table 1 and Figure 1 summarize the way in which drift, boundary proximity, clipping and inefficiency depend

on curvature. Through the complete set of curvature values explored, the average relative radius is increasing monotonically with the curvature parameter c , and hence the monotonic increase in the average relative radius with curvature parameter c .

Table 1: Curvature sweep summary. Drift AUC corresponds to Pixel vs Geodesic drift.

c	Drift AUC (Ins)	Drift AUC (Del)	Rel. radius (Ins)	Rel. radius (Del)	Clamp frac (Ins)	Clamp frac (Del)	Ineff (Ins)	Ineff (Del)
0.25	0.454	0.427	0.760	0.757	0.982	0.945	2.97	2.64
0.50	0.423	0.454	0.887	0.884	0.975	0.938	4.20	3.92
1.00	0.395	0.477	0.963	0.962	0.978	0.946	7.61	7.59
2.00	0.362	0.507	0.993	0.992	0.983	0.937	15.71	16.78
4.00	0.400	0.462	0.999	0.999	0.976	0.928	25.59	26.37

Observed trends. Insertion drift decreases from $c = 0.25 \rightarrow c = 2.00$ and then stabilizes, while deletion drift increases with curvature, peaking at $c = 2.00$. In parallel, clamp saturation remains high (especially for insertion), consistent with boundary-adjacent embeddings at larger curvature.

Figure 1: Curvature sweeps diagnostics: (a) mean drift AUC (Pixel vs Geodesic) for insertion/deletion; (b) mean relative radius $\sqrt{c}\|z\|$; (c) norm-clamp saturation fraction.

6.6.2 Faithfulness Curves

Figure 2 shows the average insertion and deletion curves as a function of normalized hyperbolic arc-length, s . At $c = 1.00$, tangent-space insertion has the maximized AUC of the path of the curve (which is the case of the maximum insertion), whereas geodesic-space deletion maintains high confidence in a longer portion of the path of the curve (which is reflected in a larger deletion AUC), and therefore signals low pixel-level insertion faithfulness at the geodesic ordering.

Table 2: Summary metrics at curvature $c = 1.00$ (mean \pm std across images). For insertion AUC, higher is better; for deletion AUC, lower is better.

Measure	Pixel	Tangent	Geodesic	Pix-Tan	Pix-Geo	Pix-Ctrl
Insertion AUC (fraction)	0.699 ± 0.209	0.672 ± 0.178	0.515 ± 0.197			
Deletion AUC (fraction)	0.373 ± 0.352	0.399 ± 0.282	0.515 ± 0.197			
Insertion AUC (arc-length)	0.580 ± 0.241	0.636 ± 0.179	0.504 ± 0.186			
Deletion AUC (arc-length)	0.388 ± 0.317	0.420 ± 0.248	0.504 ± 0.186			
Drift AUC (insertion)				0.272 ± 0.141	0.394 ± 0.238	0.391 ± 0.240
Drift AUC (deletion)				0.429 ± 0.138	0.480 ± 0.136	0.477 ± 0.134
Drift max (insertion)				0.596 ± 0.259	0.882 ± 0.119	0.867 ± 0.134
Drift max (deletion)				0.923 ± 0.074	0.981 ± 0.027	0.980 ± 0.027

Observation. Numerically, the arc-length insertion AUC ranks *Tangent* $>$ *Pixel* $>$ *Geodesic*, while deletion AUC ranks *Pixel* $<$ *Tangent* $<$ *Geodesic* (lower is better). Drift summaries show that Pixel–Tangent alignment is consistently tighter than Pixel–Geodesic, particularly for deletion.

Figure 2: Mean insertion (left) and deletion (right) curves parameterized by normalized hyperbolic arc-length s ($c = 1.00$).

6.6.3 Drift Curves and Distributions

Figure 3 shows the drift trajectories for insertion and deletion when comparing external Pixel progress with internal Tangent and Geodesic progress under the same intrinsic parameterization.

Figure 3: Mean drift curves for insertion (left) and deletion (right), comparing external Pixel progress to internal Tangent/Geodesic/Control progress ($c = 1.00$).

6.6.4 Drift and Path Inefficiency

Figure 4 examines the relationship between drift AUC and external path inefficiency \mathcal{I} . The scatter patterns indicate multiple operating regimes. Higher inefficiency is associated with reduced Pixel–Tangent drift (especially for deletion), consistent with boundary constraints and clamp effects causing progress trajectories to saturate and reducing visible mismatch.

Figure 4: Drift AUC versus external path inefficiency \mathcal{I} for insertion (top-left) and deletion (top-right), with the inefficiency distribution shown below ($c = 1.00$).

6.6.5 Boundary Amplification and Theoretical Diagnostics

Figure 5 provides two complementary diagnostics. First, the λ_{\max} -saturation trend links maximum relative radius and boundary amplification, showing near-constant high amplification across images. Second, theorem-ratio curves compare stepwise change against a 1-Lipschitz-style bound: pixel/tangent ratios remain near zero, while the geodesic ratio approaches the bound with a clear mid-trajectory dip, indicating non-uniform geodesic progression.

Figure 5: Theoretical and boundary-regime diagnostics ($c = 1.00$): theorem-ratio curves for insertion (top-left), deletion (top-right), and λ_{\max} saturation versus maximum relative radius (bottom).

Within the hyperbolic latent space, the conformal factor

$$\lambda_c(z) = \frac{2}{1 - c\|z\|^2} = \frac{2}{1 - r^2}, \quad r = \sqrt{c}\|z\|$$

shows a strong enhancement as r gets closer to unity. As a result, trajectories that come close to the boundary undergo a large local amplification of the metric.

Our empirical assessment based on the λ_{\max} -saturation diagnostic unambiguously shows that the external trajectories are already in a constricted near-boundary regime. The maximum relative radius is grouped around $\sqrt{c}\|z\|_{\max} \approx 0.964$, while $\lambda_{\max} \approx 28.31$ in all instances and has a very small coefficient of variation, $CV \approx 5.3 \times 10^{-7}$. In addition, clamp saturation reaches about 98%. Hence, although boundary amplification is evidently active, the peak amplification is effectively saturated throughout the sample set. Here, λ_{\max} alone is not enough to explain the whole heterogeneity seen in drift but is instead more properly interpreted as a regime indicator that confirms operation close to the boundary rather than as a sample-specific predictor. Drift continues despite clamped operation because trajectories remain close enough to the boundary that the hyperbolic metric can still exaggerate the accumulated displacement. Accordingly, the observed drift is more fruitfully explicated in terms of path-level metrics, such as path inefficiency, average operating radius, and cumulative traversal geometry, than through the single maximum value of λ .

6.6.6 Prototype Structure in Hyperbolic Space

Figure 6 summarizes prototype geometry in hyperbolic space: the pairwise prototype-distance matrix (left) and hierarchy-grouped mean distances (right). Distances are smallest within the same leaf class, larger within the same superclass, and largest across superclasses, consistent with hierarchical separation in hyperbolic representations.

Figure 6: Prototype structure in hyperbolic space ($c = 1.00$): pairwise prototype-distance heatmap (left) and mean distances grouped by hierarchy relation (right).

6.6.7 Summary Interpretation and Correlation Evidence

Table 3: Selected Pearson correlations (r) between drift AUC and regime diagnostics at $c = 1.00$.

Regime	Drift metric	Diagnostic variable	r
Insertion	Pix-Tan drift AUC	Path inefficiency \mathcal{I} (ins)	-0.58
Insertion	Pix-Tan drift AUC	Mean relative radius $\sqrt{c}\ z\ $ (ins)	-0.00
Insertion	Pix-Tan drift AUC	Clamp saturation fraction (ins)	+0.02
Deletion	Pix-Tan drift AUC	Path inefficiency \mathcal{I} (del)	-0.79
Deletion	Pix-Tan drift AUC	Mean relative radius $\sqrt{c}\ z\ $ (del)	+0.36
Deletion	Pix-Tan drift AUC	Clamp saturation fraction (del)	+0.42
Deletion	Pix-Geo drift AUC	Mean relative radius $\sqrt{c}\ z\ $ (del)	+0.32
Deletion	Pix-Geo drift AUC	Path inefficiency \mathcal{I} (del)	-0.66

6.7 Discussion

The observed results should be seen as a discussion of the relationship between the mechanisms of exter-

nal and internal perturbation during faithfulness assessment, rather than as a statement that standard evaluation does not work. External insertion and deletion are also useful tests of whether high-ranked pixels have a stronger effect on model output compared with irrelevant or random pixels [1][13]. What the two-way framework brings on board is an additional consistency check: using the common ruler, denoted as $\Delta(z) = d_c(z, p_{\hat{y}})$, the normalized evolution $P(s)$, and the drift $D(s) = |P_{\text{ext}}(s) - P_{\text{int}}(s)|$, it measures the agreement between externally effective relevance and internally consistent semantic change. Drift, in this sense, is not a substitute for external faithfulness evaluation, but rather an extension of it, as it quantifies the consistency between externally effective relevance and internally consistent semantic change.

According to our findings, this agreement is only partial. The signal of meaningful faithfulness is maintained by pixel perturbations, but the externally induced path, $z_{\text{ext}}(s)$, is not entirely consistent with the internal reference paths, particularly under deletion. The fact that Pixel lies consistently closer to Tangent than to Geodesic is informative: external masking is propagated by the local differential structure of the nonlinear map, namely $\psi(x) = \text{Proj}_c(\exp_0^c(E(x)))$, whereas the geodesic is determined only by the endpoints and minimizes intrinsic length, $L_c(\gamma) = d_c(z_0, z_1)$. The resulting Pixel-Geodesic disagreement is therefore a conflict of mechanisms rather than a conflict of class semantics.

There are various identifiable factors that may cause drift, including masking and baseline-substitution artifacts, perturbation transport through the encoder Jacobian, and hyperbolic amplification through the conformal factor $\lambda(z) = \frac{2}{1-c\|z\|^2}$ [14]. Since the external paths are already in a near-boundary regime, that is, saturated in the value of λ_{\max} , the residual variation in drift is more likely to be due to path-level quantities, including the inefficiency of the external paths, namely $\mathcal{I}_{\text{ext}} = \frac{L_{\text{ext}}}{d_c(z_0, z_1)}$, the mean operating radius, and the geometry of cumulative traversal. Drift thus improves faithfulness analysis by showing whether an externally effective explanation is also internally semantically consistent, and when residual disparity is more likely to arise because of perturbation artifacts, local encoder sensitivity, or the geometry of hyperbolic paths.

7 Conclusion

To conclude, the paper examined the connection between external perturbations on pixel space and internally geometry-consistent perturbations on the calculation of faithfulness of hyperbolic prototype-based classifiers. External insertion and deletion tests still are traditional perturbation tests to test whether highly ranked pixels have more influence on model output than irrelevant pixels or pixels picked at random [1].

At the same time, more recent studies, as represented by A Consistent and Efficient Evaluation Strategy for Attribution Methods [2][3] and by Metrics for saliency map evaluation of deep learning explanation methods,

have shown that perturbation based scores can be corrupted by masking artefacts, information leakage and out-of-distribution artifacts, and should be interrogated more carefully on their semantic interpretation.

To formalize the comparison, we introduced a two-sided formulation including a shared semantic reference $\Delta(z) = d_c(z, p_{\hat{y}})$ the endpoint normalized progression function $P(s)$, and the drift measure $D(s) = |P_{ext}(s) - P_{int}(s)|$, therefore, as to evaluate the alignment between aexternal perturbation paths and internally coherent semantic motion and responses. The major empirical finding that can be observed after the analysis is that the signal of external faithfulness is preserved, but it is realized only in part in accordance with the internal semantic geometry of the model. Pixel-wise perturbations have a better coherence to and consistency with the tangent space than the geodesic controls, suggesting that conceivable masking operations are more propagated by local differential responses and structures than by global optimal or smallest manifold motions. This is in line with the results of previous works done with saliency checks [50], in which explanation measurements require additional than a solitary superficial diagnosis. In a hyperbolic embedding space, in addition to the inherent Poincare geometry the observed discrepancy is also enhanced by the conformal factor, which gives a compact hierarchical representational capacity, and the conformal factor which enhances path-dependent effects near the boundary[14][16].

Together, the findings show that drift can neither replace classical perturbation-based faithfulness measures but can help to highlight those situations where an externally useful explanation coincides with internal semantic consistency, and can also be used to point out where residual divergence is due to masking artefacts, local encoder sensitivity, or geometry of hyperbolic pathways[3].

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A Supplementary Quantitative Summary

It is a derived summary and supplementary diagnostics that support but do not repeat the key discoveries described in Section 6, and this is described in this appendix. Instead of reflecting the main performance tables, the appendix focuses on three subset research questions: how drift varies across curvature regimes, the degree to which at our boundary of interest, namely $c = 1.00$, the Pixel trajectories do not follow Tangent and Geodesic references, and whether the observed discrepancy is consistent with the behavior of a boundary-dominated operational regime. As a result, the retained measures are diagnostically-oriented as opposed to primary: mean drift, maximum drift, external path inefficiency, relative radius, and conformal amplification.

The appendix uses the same notation as the main text. In particular, the principal diagnostics remain the mean drift

$$D_{\text{mean}} = \int_0^1 |P_{\text{ext}}(s) - P_{\text{int}}(s)| ds,$$

the maximum drift

$$D_{\text{max}} = \sup_{s \in [0,1]} |P_{\text{ext}}(s) - P_{\text{int}}(s)|,$$

the external path inefficiency

$$\mathcal{I} = \frac{L_{\text{ext}}}{d_c(z_0, z_1)},$$

the relative radius

$$r = \sqrt{c} \|z\|,$$

and the conformal amplification factor

$$\lambda(z) = \frac{2}{1 - r^2}.$$

A.1 Cross-curvature Diagnostic Trends

The diagnostic variables define two different patterns across the sweep of the curvature. The regime indicators, relative radius and path inefficiency, show a monotonic growth with increasing curvature, and thus the operation point moves towards the boundary gradually, and the externally forced paths are becoming less efficient relative to the intrinsic distance. However, drift itself is not a strictly monotonic pattern: insertion drift decreases and levels off, deletion drift increases and levels off, but at $c = 2.00$, the pattern shows a small drop, and at $c = 4.00$, the pattern starts to decrease again significantly. The implication of this splitting is that the geometric operating regime is dominated by curvature and the final scale of drift depends on geometry as well as the interactions between the perturbation-path.

A.2 Derived Disagreement Summaries at $c = 1.00$

The Pixel–Tangent comparison is closest to the internal reference in both the insertion and deletion, whereas

Table 4: Derived cross-curvature trend summary based on the sweep diagnostics.

Metric	Overall trend	Peak / minimum	Interpretation
Insertion drift AUC	Decreases, then stabilizes	Minimum near $c = 2.00$	Partial reduction before plateau
Deletion drift AUC	Rises, then slightly falls	Peak at $c = 2.00$	Non-monotonic drift response
Mean relative radius	Monotonic increase	Largest at $c = 4.00$	Increasing boundary proximity
Path inefficiency	Strong monotonic increase	Largest at $c = 4.00$	Increasing intrinsic wandering
Clamp saturation	Persistently high	No sharp transition	Stable clamp-dominated regime

Figure 7: Supplementary curvature sweep summary showing: (a) mean drift AUC for Pixel vs Geodesic under insertion and deletion, (b) mean relative radius $\sqrt{c} \|z\|$, and (c) norm-clamp saturation fraction across the tested curvature values.

Table 5: Derived drift-gap summary at $c = 1.00$. Gap is computed as Pix–Geo – Pix–Tan.

Statistic	Pix–Tan	Pix–Geo	Gap	Interpretation
Insertion drift AUC	0.272	0.394	0.122	Larger geodesic mismatch
Deletion drift AUC	0.429	0.480	0.051	Smaller but persistent mismatch
Insertion drift max	0.596	0.882	0.286	Strong local-vs-geodesic split
Deletion drift max	0.923	0.981	0.058	Near-saturated disagreement

Table 6: Selected Pearson correlations (r) between drift AUC and regime diagnostics at $c = 1.00$.

Regime	Drift metric	Diagnostic variable	r
Insertion	Pix–Tan drift AUC	Path inefficiency \mathcal{I} (ins)	-0.58
Insertion	Pix–Tan drift AUC	Mean relative radius $\sqrt{c} \ z\ $ (ins)	-0.00
Insertion	Pix–Tan drift AUC	Clamp saturation fraction (ins)	+0.02
Deletion	Pix–Tan drift AUC	Path inefficiency \mathcal{I} (del)	-0.79
Deletion	Pix–Tan drift AUC	Mean relative radius $\sqrt{c} \ z\ $ (del)	+0.36
Deletion	Pix–Tan drift AUC	Clamp saturation fraction (del)	+0.42
Deletion	Pix–Geo drift AUC	Mean relative radius $\sqrt{c} \ z\ $ (del)	+0.32
Deletion	Pix–Geo drift AUC	Path inefficiency \mathcal{I} (del)	-0.66

the Pixel–Geodesic comparison is more discordant at the given curvature $c = 1.00$. The difference between Pixel–Geodesic and Pixel–Tangent drift is larger during the insertion than during the deletion process, and this goes to show that the main difference between local and geodesic internal motion is most apparent during feature recovery. The same trend is also present in the maximum-drift statistics, where the insertion has significantly broader separation of the two internal references, compared to deletion. As a result, the results confirm the explanation that external perturbations tend to propagate with more local differential structures than with globally shortest manifold paths.

A.3 Boundary-regime and Prototype Diagnostics

A boundary-dominated operating condition is supported by the auxiliary regime diagnostics. Relative radius is high, clamp activity is high, and external path inefficiency is significantly above the geodesic base, hence demonstrating that the observed external trajectory is not a mere short intrinsic movement between common endpoints. At the same time, the prototype-distance structure preserves the expected hierarchical organisation with shorter distances between smaller semantic groupings and greater distances between larger categories. Combined, these facilitating diagnostics imply that the recorded external–internal mismatch is

Figure 8: Representative response curves at $c = 1.00$. Top: insertion response under normalized hyperbolic arc-length parameterization. Bottom: deletion response under normalized fraction-of-features-removed parameterization.

Figure 9: Representative drift curves at $c = 1.00$. Top: insertion drift, comparing Pixel vs Tangent, Pixel vs Geodesic, and Pixel vs Control under the common intrinsic parameterization. Bottom: deletion drift under the same comparison setting.

Table 7: Regime interpretation summary at $c = 1.00$.

Diagnostic	Observed pattern	Interpretation
Relative radius	High (≈ 0.96)	Near-boundary operation
Clamp saturation	Persistently high	Norm-limited traversal is active
Path inefficiency	$\gg 1$ for both paths	External path is not geodesic-like
λ_{\max} variability	Extremely small	Saturated amplification regime
Prototype distances	Hierarchically ordered	Stable semantic geometry retained

stable on a hyperbolic class geometry.

Table 8: Prototype-geometry summary used in the appendix interpretation.

Hierarchy relation	Relative distance pattern
Same leaf	Smallest
Same superclass	Intermediate
Different superclass	Largest

Figure 10: Supplementary regime diagnostics. Top: λ_{\max} saturation diagnostic showing boundary-dominated operation. Bottom: distribution of external path inefficiency $I = L_{\text{ext}}/d_c(z_0, z_1)$ for insertion and deletion.

Figure 11: Prototype distance matrix in hyperbolic space, used as supplementary evidence for the hierarchical organization of the prototype geometry.